

NOTES

 $\rho\sigma$ Relationship in the Oxidation of Substituted Toluenes by Ce^{IV}

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In our previous communication¹, we reported the oxidation of toluene and substituted toluenes mainly with electron withdrawing substituents. It was reported that the reaction is total second order and the ρ value is -1.7 and evidences were presented to show that it is mainly a radical process.

This communication deals with the oxidation of toluenes with electron donating groups. There is a remarkable change of oxidation course and it appears that these oxidations with electron donating groups follow a different mechanism, involving a two electron oxidation under these conditions. These reactions are also total second order and the products are also similar as found earlier. The rate constants for xylenes, methoxy toluenes and toluenes with electron withdrawing substituents are given in Tables I, II and III respectively.

TABLE I

Second Order Rate Constants (litre mol⁻¹ min⁻¹) for the oxidation of xylenes at 35°, in the presence of $HClO_4$

Solvent % HOAc-H ₂ O v/v	$HClO_4(M)$	para	meta	ortho
50	1.0	3.046	0.8973	1.556
60	1.0	7.964	2.125	3.075
70	1.0	13.9	5.176	8.363
50	1.25	5.828	1.674	3.027
50	1.50	11.74	3.365	6.040

TABLE II

Second Order Rate Constants (litre mol⁻¹ min⁻¹) for the oxidation of toluene and methoxy toluenes at 35°, in the presence of 0.10M $HClO_4$

Solvent % HOAc-H ₂ O v/v	Toluene	<i>p</i> -methoxy toluene	<i>m</i> -methoxy toluene	<i>o</i> -methoxy toluene
50	0.0169	33.57	3.131	6.681
60	0.0277	73.04	6.910	12.710
70	0.0568	106.50	11.390	22.850

TABLE III

Second Order Rate Constants (litre mol⁻¹ min⁻¹) for the oxidation of toluene and substituted toluenes at 35°, in the presence of HClO_4

Solvent % HOAc-H ₂ O v/v	HClO ₄ (M)	Toluene	p-nitro toluene	m-nitro toluene	m-chloro toluene
50	1.0	0.3249	0.0160	0.0284	0.0639
60	1.0	0.4772	0.0761	0.0812	0.1437
70	1.0	0.8706	0.1609	0.1777	0.3282
50	1.25	0.6555	0.0327	0.0563	0.1284
50	1.50	1.2640	0.0656	0.1133	0.2774

The most important point noted is the ρ value of -4.3 for xylenes and -4.5 for methoxy toluenes, as against -1.7 noted earlier for toluenes with electron withdrawing groups. A combined plot (Figure 1) is given, indicating the abrupt change in the ρ value suggesting a change in mechanism from electron withdrawing substituents to electron releasing groups in these oxidations. This indicates that an ionic process² is operating when electron donating substituents are present, and a one electron transfer takes place when electron withdrawing substituents are present.

Fig. 1.

2. H. C. Brown and Y. Oka-oto, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 485; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 4980.

It will be seen from Table II that the meta methoxy group is also accelerating the reaction much against its σ^+ value (+0.047). It is presumed that probably the electron withdrawing nature of meta methoxy group as seen by its σ^+ value is true for reactions which require electron recession at the site of the reaction. But from the nature of ρ value for xylenes and methoxy toluenes, it seems that these reactions are ionic processes which require electron accession. It is clear in view of the above that the σ^+ value for meta methoxy is not applicable for reactions which require electron accession like the reaction under consideration. It may be made clear that the methoxy group at ortho and para positions involves resonance effect, and the same effect probably operates from meta position, otherwise the rates cannot be rationalized as

in the case of methoxy toluenes. Resonance effect at meta position has to be invoked, as suggested by Gould³ :

“When the substituent and the reaction centre lie meta to each other, here due to the alternating nature of the atoms in a conjugated system, resonance effect becomes less, although they do not, as might be supposed, entirely disappear.”

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Received April 1, 1970

3. E. S. Gould, "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry", Holt, Reinhart and Winston, New York, 1965, p. 219.